

THE HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION OF SOLUTIONS CONTAINING ZINC HYDROXIDE AND SODIUM HYDROXIDE.

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In continuation of the work described before the hydrogen ion concentration of solutions containing ZnO and Na₂O in varying proportions has been determined using the glass electrode. The results obtained previously are confirmed and it is inferred that in solutions more dilute than 6N, the sodium zincate is largely hydrolysed, whereas in concentrated solutions the hydrolysis is small. The possibility of isolating sodium zincate from solutions stronger than 8N has been suggested.

The data obtained by measuring the electrical conductivity of solutions containing zinc hydroxide and sodium hydroxide have been discussed in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 223). In order to get further information regarding these solutions, the determination of hydrogen ion concentration was undertaken as it affords an important method for the study of acid-base equilibria. The usefulness of the method in the study of the zincate problem has been already recognised.

Kunschert (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 41, 337), who made a potentiometric study of alkaline solutions containing zinc hydroxide, inferred that in these solutions zinc is present chiefly in the form of ZnO₂ ions, which are partly hydrolysed into HZnO₂ and OH ions. Fricke and Ahrndts (*ibid.*, 1924, 134, 344) made similar measurements using mercuric oxide electrode and came to the conclusion that an alkali zincate is formed in strongly alkaline solutions. On the other hand, Hildebrand and Bowers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 785) titrated potentiometrically solutions of zinc halides by means of an alkali and from the curves obtained by plotting the volume of sodium hydroxide against E.M.F. suggested that (i) weak acids of the type HZnCl₃ exist in solution, and (ii) a solution of zinc hydroxide in sodium hydroxide behaves both as a colloid and as a mono-basic acid.

Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2120) examined the behaviour of zinc hydroxide during its precipitation from a solution of zinc sulphate by means of sodium hydroxide. He observed that zinc hydroxide was precipitated at a p_H 5.2 and that the solubility product calculated from this value is not in agreement with that already known. He considered that the precipitated zinc hydroxide contained no basic

salt which was formed during the titration and that there was no indication of the acidic nature of the hydroxide when alkali was added to redissolve the precipitate. Britton and Robinson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 540) used the glass electrode in the study of this problem and observed that the precipitation of zinc hydroxide from a solution of zinc sulphate takes place at a somewhat lower p_H than from the corresponding solution of zinc chloride. They were, however, unable to reproduce the p_H curves obtained by Kolthoff and Kameda (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 832) and by Prytz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 200, 133).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The hydrogen ion concentration of solutions prepared as described in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*) and containing the different amounts of zinc hydroxide and sodium hydroxide (expressed as the ratio $ZnO : Na_2O$) was measured using the glass electrode. The valve unit required for the measurement of the E.M.F. of the glass electrode system was constructed according to the details given by Mehta (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1936, 5, ii, 77). The apparatus was standardised by means of buffer solutions of known p_H . Two such solutions, *viz.*, $M/20$ -potassium hydrogen phthalate (p_H 3.97) and $M/20$ -borax (p_H 9.15) were used. The former was prepared according to the method of Dodge (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1915, 7, 29; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1655) and the latter was Merck's G. R. quality.

The Morton glass electrode cell was placed in an electrically heated thermostat which was zinc-lined and earthed. Its temperature was maintained constant at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The E.M.F. of the combination

was measured with the help of the valve unit referred to above. From the observed E.M.F. the p_H was calculated by means of the equation,

$$p_H = \frac{0.4535 - E}{0.06}$$

The glass electrode was checked immediately before and after each set of readings. The p_H values calculated from the observed E.M.F. and checked by means of the calibration curve are given in the following table in which N denotes concentration of the solution in normality of its sodium hydroxide content.

TABLE I.

N.	Ratios of ZnO:Na ₂ O					
	1:1.76.	1:2.44.	1:3.03.	1:3.55.	1:4.05.	
9.41	9.297	—	—	—	—	
9.20	—	9.375	—	—	—	
9.50	—	—	9.275	—	—	
9.48	—	—	—	9.417	—	
9.47	—	—	—	—	9.433	
8	9.783	9.625	9.668	9.762	9.808	
6	10.262	10.142	10.195	10.272	10.375	
4	10.653	10.548	10.495	10.643	10.638	
3	11.015	10.763	10.742	10.855	10.862	
2	—	10.992	10.880	11.027	11.017	
1.5	—	11.083	11.012	11.170	11.200	
1	—	—	11.200	11.302	11.362	

DISCUSSION.

It will be noticed from the table that the p_H of all the solutions used in this investigation increases with dilution and that it lies between 9 and 12. When the p_H is plotted against concentration, curves are obtained (only one illustrative curve is shown in Fig. 1A) which show that the p_H increases at first rapidly, then slowly for some time and finally rapidly once again as the dilution is increased.

FIG. 1.

 ZnO : Na₂O = 1 : 1.76.

If, however, the hydroxyl ion concentration calculated by means of the equation

$$\log \frac{1}{[\text{OH}']} = pK_w - p_H = 13.725 - p_H$$

is plotted against concentration, curves of the type illustrated in Fig. 1B are obtained which show that the hydroxyl ion concentration increases at first slowly and then rapidly with dilution.

The increase in p_H or OH' ion concentration on dilution referred to above appears to be due to an increase in the hydrolysis of sodium zincate present in the concentrated solutions. It was stated in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*) that the increase in the equivalent conductivity of these solutions on dilution is to be attributed to an increase in the number of mobile hydroxyl ions. The data presented in this paper confirm the above statement.

FIG. 2.

When the p_H is plotted against the ratio $\text{ZnO}:\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, curves are

obtained (*vide* Fig. 2) which are concave towards the ratio axis. These curves are similar to those obtained by plotting the equivalent conductivity against the ratio ZnO: Na₂O described in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). This fact leads one to infer that the variation in the equivalent conductivity just referred to is to be ascribed to a change in p_H of the solutions. It is clearly seen from the curves that the p_H decreases with an increase in the relative amount of sodium hydroxide, reaches a minimum and then increases again. In other words as the ratio ZnO: Na₂O is decreased, there is at first a decrease in p_H followed by an increase. This behaviour of the solutions may be explained as being due to a diminution in the hydrolysis of sodium zincate on the addition of sodium hydroxide. In accordance with this explanation the minimum points of the different curves correspond to the maximum repression of hydrolysis after which there is an increase in p_H owing to the hydroxyl ions coming from the added alkali.

The variation in hydroxyl ion concentration with a change in the ratio ZnO: Na₂O is represented graphically in Fig. 3 from which it is seen

FIG. 3.

that the nature of these curves is similar to that of the curves in Fig. 2 with this difference, however, that the variation in OH' ion concentration with a change in the ratio ZnO: Na₂O is more pronounced than the variation in p_H . It is also seen from Fig. 3 that in solutions, more concentrated than 6*N*, the OH ion concentration diminishes but little on decreasing the ratio ZnO: Na₂O. This behaviour may be due to the fact that in these concentrated solutions the sodium zincate present is hydrolysed only to a small extent and that therefore there is no marked change in OH ion concentration on increasing the relative proportion of sodium hydroxide.

The behaviour of solutions more dilute than 6*N* is different. The OH ion concentration falls in the beginning, reaches a minimum and then increases again. It seems probable that in dilute solutions sodium zincate is largely hydrolysed and that the relative increase in the amount of sodium hydroxide represses the hydrolysis with a consequential decrease in the hydroxyl ion concentration until the minimum value is reached. After this point further increase in the relative proportion of sodium hydroxide has very little effect on the hydrolysis of sodium zincate and the OH ion concentration increases due to the hydroxyl ions coming from the alkali.

From the results obtained in this investigation and the conclusions arrived at above it appears that it should be possible to isolate sodium zincate from solutions stronger than 8*N*. This has been confirmed and the details of the experiments in which sodium zincate was isolated in a state of purity will be published shortly.

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Received July 10, 1939.
